

A Study of Complex Formation of Some Thiophene Derivatives with Metal Ions : Part II.

BASUDEV DE and A. K. CHAUDHURY*

Department of Chemistry, University of Burdwan, Burdwan, West Bengal

Manuscript received 29 August 1974; revised 3 May 1976; accepted 7 June 1976

Formation constants of ligands, (I) thiophene-2-carboxylic acid (T2CA); (II) tetrahydrothiophene-2-carboxylic acid (THT2CA); (III) acetic acid; (IV) *m*-nitrobenzoic acid; (V) *o*-chlorobenzoic acid; with metal ions, Ag(I); Hg(II); Fe(II); Co(II); Mn(II) and Tl(I) are studied. M-S π interaction in complexes between I and Fe(II) and between II and Ag(I), Hg(II) and Fe(II) has been suggested. Irving and Williams order is violated by Fe(II) in complexes with I and II.

STABILITY constants of the complexes formed by some thiophene derivatives used as ligands (I) thiophene 2-carboxylic acid (T2CA), (II) tetrahydrothiophene 2-carboxylic acid (THT2CA) as well as with some other carboxylic acids, (III) acetic acid, (IV) *m*-nitrobenzoic acid and (V) *o*-chlorobenzoic acid (ligands III, IV and V were included for comparison) with some metal ions Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) are already reported¹. The study is extended to examine the behaviour of some diverse metal ions e.g., silver(I), mercury(II), iron(II), cobalt(II), manganese(II) and thallium(I).

Some of these are strong soft acids² [Ag(I) and Hg(II)] while others have mixed hard and soft character. Iron, cobalt and manganese in their lower oxidation states, tend to become soft acids, because of greater availability of the electrons in the low-lying 'd' orbitals, which can be used for π -back-donation. Thallium(I) on the other hand is harder than thallium(III) because the filled S-shell in the former case hinders formation of the dative π bond. Silver(I) and mercury(II) generally prefer coordination number two, the coordination bonds being linearly disposed.

Experimental

Preparation of the ligands and experimental procedures have been reported¹. Perchlorates of manganese(II) and silver(I) were prepared by neutralisation of manganese carbonate and silver hydroxide with perchloric acid. Mercuric(II) and thallic(I) perchlorates were prepared by double decomposition between mercuric chloride and silver perchlorate and between barium perchlorate and thallic sulphate. Metals were estimated as Mn(NH₄)PO₄, H₂O, AgCl, HgS^(a) and Tl₂CrO₄^(b). Ferrous and cobaltous perchlorates were prepared by passing ferrous sulphate and cobaltous chloride solution separately through a cation exchanger⁴ (Amberlite I-R, 120) in hydrogen form, until the pH of the entrant and issuing solution are the same. After this, the excess metal salt was

washed out with distilled water, and then barium perchlorate was allowed to pass in, whereby, barium free eluates containing pure perchlorates of Fe(II) and Co(II) were obtained. The solutions were kept in volumetric flasks in an oxygen free nitrogen atmosphere. Analyses of these solutions were also done by passing the measured volumes of the solutions through the cation exchanger in hydrogen form and measuring the acid liberated.

The solution for metal titration contained in most cases : 0.001M metal ion, 0.005M ligand, 0.0025M perchloric acid and 0.1M NaClO₄ in 20 ml of 1 : 1 aqueous dioxane. The titrations were carried out in an atmosphere of pure nitrogen at temperature 30° ± 0.1°.

Results and Discussion

The stability constants are calculated assuming in general a maximum coordination of two, with the aid of the equation⁵ and by the method of least squares.

$$\frac{\bar{n}}{(\bar{n}-1)[L]} = \frac{(2-\bar{n})[L]}{(\bar{n}-1)} K_1 K_2 - K_1$$

When the $\bar{n}$ values do not go above one, only log K_1 is calculated by the equation, $\log K_1 = pL$

+ $\log \frac{\bar{n}}{(1-\bar{n})}$. But in a few cases both log K_1 and log K_2 are calculated, although the $\bar{n}$ values did not go above 1. Some of the values were also recalculated by the algebraic methods of Block and McIntyre⁶.

The log ${}^pK_1^H$ values of the ligands, the log K values as well as the maximum $\bar{n}$ are given in the Table 1.

The relation between log K_1 and log ${}^pK_1^H$ is shown in Fig. 1. Lines are drawn between ligands I and III which are assumed to be nonchelating. For

Fe(II) and Mn(II) lines are drawn between ligands I and II. These lines are nearly parallel with the former lines. It is noticed that the values of $\log K_1$ for Ag(I) and Hg(II) with ligand II are very much above the lines for the metal ions. This indicates stronger interaction, which may be due to chelation. The $\log K_1$ values with ligands IV and V are also often much off the lines. The reason may be that, the nitro- or chloro-benzoates cannot be compared with the thiophene carboxylates, although the linking is through carboxylate oxygen. There may be other reasons like polymerisation, but chelation can hardly be inferred in these cases.

$\log K_2 > \log K_1$. The reason is the strong tendency of Ag(I) to form linear bonds with similar ligands⁹.

Mercury(II) forms stronger complexes than silver. With THT2CA the titration showed an initial $\bar{n}$ value very high (about 1.4) and also some precipitation taking place. The experiments were repeated with a lower ligand-metal ratio 1 : 2. The comparatively larger $\log K_1$ value suggest some M-S π interaction. With both the ligands I and II $\log K_1 > \log K_2$. The second complex has probably the linear structure (L-M-L) with some M-S π interaction in case of ligand II only. Here the metal is linked through

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log K_1^M$ vs. $\log PK_1^H$ for metal complexes.

With silver(I) ion T2CA does not show any extra-activity. THT2CA and to some extent ligands IV and V show greater affinity. In course of titration with II and Ag(I), the colour of the solution turned pink, possibly due to the charge transfer interaction of the Ag-S bond. Hence M-S π interaction and therefore chelation can be suggested. Considering the molecular parameters⁷ of the ligand II and Ag(I) ion it is found that in the monochelate silver is slightly distorted from its linearity and is possibly tetrahedrally surrounded by the ligand and water molecules. For the 1 : 2 complex $\log K_2 > \log K_1$. This may be due to (1) bischelation, (2) coordination of two ligand molecules through sulphur, (3) coordination of two ligand molecules through carboxylate oxygen, (4) coordination of the second ligand molecule through sulphur to the central atom of the monochelate.

Arguments against the second possibility is that such strong bonding with sulphur in preference to carboxylate oxygen is not possible as the sulphur is not charged as in mercaptides⁸. The third possibility finds support in the fact that $\log K_2 > \log K_1$ in case of acetate also. But the evidences of M-S π interaction go against this. With the ligand III

carboxylate oxygen. This is justified as K_1 and K_2 for mercury complexes are equivalent but K_3 and K_4 are much less¹⁰. Here with II $\log K_1$ is 4.36 and $\log K_2$ is 3.44. So bischelation cannot be suggested.

Iron(II) provides remarkable results. The stabilities are quite high in comparison. For ligands I and II Irving and Williams¹¹ order is violated only by Fe(II). With these ligands I and II the order of stabilities is¹

This can be explained by a strong Fe-S π interaction. The comparatively stronger interaction of thiophene sulphur in I with Fe(II) is worth noting. Any enhanced stabilisation with ligand II is not however observed, but it was found that $\log K_2 > \log K_1$ in this case, where as $\log K_1 > \log K_2$ in case of ligand I. In the experiments with ligand I and II the pH never exceeded 4.5 and the starting $\bar{n}$'s were quite high (0.82 for I and 1.02 for II). In both the cases the colour of the solution changed to greenish yellow.

A tentative value of $\log K_3$ with ligand I is calculated by half integral method from the formation

TABLE I.—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL LIGAND COMPLEXES AT $30.0^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$ IN 50% V/V WATER-DIOXANE MEDIUM WITH 0.1M NaClO_4 BACKGROUND

Ligand	Ag(I)			Hg(II)			Fe(II)			Co(II)			Tl(I)			Mn(II)			
	log K_1	log K_2	Max $(\bar{n})$	log K_1	log K_2	Max $(\bar{n})$	log K_1	log K_2	Max $(\bar{n})$	log K_1	log K_2	Max $(\bar{n})$	log K_1	log K_2	Max $(\bar{n})$	log K_1	log K_2	Max $(\bar{n})$	
I. T-2-CA	4.98	20.3 [2.01] ^a	0.10	3.60* [3.59]	2.35 [2.33]	0.77	4.57 [4.86]	4.40† [4.31]	3.10	2.51 [2.48]	—	0.38	—	—	—	2.28 [2.27]	—	—	0.45
II. TH-T-2-CA	5.25	3.06 [3.13]	1.82	4.36+ [4.49]	3.44 [3.52]	1.35	4.58 [4.65]	4.85 [4.79]	1.82	2.59 [2.57]	—	0.54	—	2.58 [2.57]	—	2.36 [2.35]	—	—	0.68
III. Acetic acid	6.00	2.10 [2.61]	1.23	3.98+ [3.96]	—	0.66	—	—	—	2.88 [2.90]	—	0.53	—	2.85 [2.84]	—	3.16 [3.15]	—	—	0.49
IV. <i>m</i> -Nitro-Benzoic acid	4.83	2.60 [2.59]	0.42	—	—	—	—	—	—	2.68 [2.67]	2.82 [2.96]	0.96	—	2.21 [2.21]	—	3.28 [2.84]	3.33 [3.85]	—	1.68
V. <i>o</i> -Chloro benzoic acid	4.75	2.40 [2.40]	0.22	3.54+ [3.55]	—	0.59	4.17 [4.20]	4.45 [4.43]	1.76	2.45 [2.64]	—	0.58	—	2.32 [2.31]	—	3.39 [3.37]	1.78 [1.86]	—	0.80

* in 1 : 2 mixture.

^a. Values in the 3rd bracket are those obtained by calculation by Block & McIntyres' Method.

† log $K_3 = 3.32$ ($=P^L$ at $\bar{n} = 2.5$).

curve (not shown here) indicating the formation of an octahedral tris-complex with I viz. $[\text{Fe}(\text{T2CA})_3]^-$.

Cobalt(II) and manganese(II) form weaker complexes with the ligands. Log K_1 values do not change appreciably from ligand I to ligand II, suggesting no extra-interaction. With ligand IV log $K_2 > \log K_1$. This was already observed in case of Cu(II) and Ni(II) ions¹. Thallium forms weak complexes, log K_1 is quite small with ligand II. This indicates absence of interaction with sulphur and hence hard acid character of Tl(I) ion.

References

1. B. DE and A. K. CHAUDHURY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 763.
2. S. AHLAND, J. CHATT and N. R. DAVIES, *Quart. Rev. (London)*, 1958, 12, 265.
3. A. J. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, 1961; (a) p. 549; (b) p. 486.
4. E. P. SERJEANT, *Nature*, 1960, 186, 963.
5. H. IRVING and Mrs. H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3357.
6. B. P. BLOCK and G. M. MCINTYRE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5667.
7. L. PAULING, "Nature of Chemical Bond", 3rd Ed., Cornell University Press, 1960, p. 221.
8. G. R. LENZ and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 378.
9. L. ORGEL, "Introduction to Transition Metal Chemistry", Wiley, 1966, p. 85.
10. H. L. ROBERTS, "Advances in Inorganic Chemistry and Radiochemistry", (Ed.) A. G. Sharpe and H. J. Emelius, Academic Press, 1968, 11, p. 332.
11. H. M. IRVING and R. J. F. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.